

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION: PROS AND CONS

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Abstract: -

Education is an important area for the development of Social Innovations. It affects the raising of the quality of life indirectly but it gives new perspectives, a better start and widens the possibilities of various social groups. Technological Innovation is having a significant impact on educational system at all levels. Online courses, teaching aids, educational software, social networking tools and other emerging technologies are disrupting the traditional classroom environment. Innovation in education encourages students and teachers to research, explore and use all the tools to uncover something new. It also improves education because it Compete students to use a higher level of thinking to solve complex problems. Digital Technology in education is a social innovation but it has its own pros and cons. This research paper will throw light on Pros and Cons of digital technology in education on both teachers and students.

Keywords: -*Social Innovation, digital, technology education, teachers, students.*

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Introduction: -

Social innovation refers to the design and implementation of new solutions that imply conceptual, process, product, or organizational change, which ultimately aim to improve the welfare and wellbeing of individuals and communities creates a school environment that promotes increased success. According to one study, students can score up to 23% higher on tests when given technological resources. But, despite the growing research supporting technology in the classroom, advocates of brick-and-mortar learning still shy away from educational innovation. The benefits of using digital educational technology in your classroom, however, are backed by extensive educational research. Teachers who use digital

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technology in their lessons often notice that with regular use, their students develop stronger communication skills and engage more often in class. It also provides more self-directed activities and opportunities for personalized or differentiated education for students who need it. And best of all, studies suggest that a student's retention rate is highest when lessons or study sessions incorporate educational technology. Because the vast majority of jobs require technological skills, teaching students digital literacy skills is another innovative trend in education. While the two are interconnected, digital literacy does not refer to traditional reading skills. Digital literacy is the ability to access digital media and absorb it efficiently. Through innovations like typing skills software, interactive digital activities, and adaptive learning algorithms, educators can simultaneously teach their student's academic and digital literacy skills. By pairing their curriculum with social innovation, schools can make an impactful investment in child education. Use technology regularly and responsibly in class to make the most of these trends in education.

Objectives: -

- 1) To study digital technology in education as social innovation
- 2) To understand the importance of digital technology in education for teachers and students.
- 3) To study the pros and cons of digital technology in education.

Significance of Study: -

Innovation in education is about more than just technology. It's about how you can use digital technology to empower students to become lifelong learners who are agents of change. Digital Technology provides students with access to countless online resources, encouraging them to carry out research and therefore become more independent. It also simplifies learning by making concepts more digestible, for example through an instructional video. It is important to recognize that there are various learning styles and traditional education may not be catering to them all. Teachers can leverage technology to achieve new levels of productivity, implement useful digital tools to expand learning opportunities for students, and increase student support and engagement. It also enables teachers to improve their instruction methods and personalize learn

Research Methodology: - The research paper is purely based on Secondary data. The data is collected from various journals, newspaper articles, books, website etc.

Literature Review: -

Educational technology is not restricted to individual computer use. It can involve other equipment and applications, such as videoconferencing, digital television (allowing students to interact with programs at their own pace), electronic whiteboards, and digital cameras (Jackson, 2008; Education Week, 2007; McCampbell, 2002). In this 21st century, the term “technology” is an important issue in many fields including education. This is because technology has become the knowledge transfer highway in most countries. Technology integration

Nowadays has gone through innovations and transformed our societies that has totally changed the way people think, work and live (Grabe, 2007). As part of this, schools and other educational institutions which are supposed to prepare students to live in “a knowledge society” need to consider technology I education changes accordingly in their curriculum (Ghavifekr, Afshari & Amla Salleh, 2012).

Digital technology has become a foundational component in many areas of our daily lives, as well as our children’s. Within the confines of the classroom and learning environment, technology can be both beneficial and problematic for **students**. Here we discuss the pros and cons of technology in education, as well as solutions for potential challenges.

- **Pro: Using Technology Can Excite Young Students**

Today, it is not uncommon for many school age children to have first encountered technological devices as toddlers. As such, students tend to associate laptops, tablets and other similar devices with fun and excitement. Consequently, technology in the classroom not only helps to harness attention and excitement while in the classroom, but invigorates traditional learning experiences.

- **Con: Use of Technology Can Distract Students**

Computers can provide young children with access to inappropriate content or information if the proper security measures are not put in place. Website blockers, internet filters and close supervision can help to prevent children from being exposed to such, and lessons in “netiquette,” or proper use of the internet can instill good web judgment and habits at an early age.

- **Pro: Prepares Students for the Future**

Our world is only becoming more reliant on technology, and having a good understanding of common technological devices and their uses is critical to prepare children for success in primary and secondary education. It is never too early for young children to begin building skills and knowledge that they can carry through their educational and professional careers. In this sense, exposure to technology in early education is a great way to begin building a foundation for success

- **Con: Removes Children from Opportunities for Socialization**

Studies have suggested that more individuals throughout society are becoming disconnected and isolated because of the links that technology provides through social networks. Young children who spend more time engaging with devices may not spend as much time interacting with their peers—which can affect those children’s social and emotional growth. In mitigating this risk, it is important to temper “technology time” as to allow children to interact socially with family and friends.

- **Pro: Technology Encourages Spontaneous Learning**

Having access to technology can help children learn to investigate topics they find interesting. For older generations, information was not as readily available and required that children have access to traditional resources. Now, however, children have a world of information right at their fingertips. When used appropriately and monitored, technology can supplement learning in or outside the classroom by providing the outlet for children to research the topics in which they are interested a lesson about dinosaurs, for example, could be supplemented by a YouTube video, or a virtual field trip to a natural history museum.

- **Con: Technology Can Discourage Creativity**

Many technology-based games and activities are “pre-made,” allowing children to complete activities without having to problem solve in creative and imaginative ways. However, there are equally as many games that promote creative development and problem-solving skills, while serving as a fun solo or group activity. Choosing the latter, and providing a wide array of other learning tools, like manipulatives or art supplies, will ensure that your children are benefitting from their play time in a safe and constructive way.

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Technology is becoming ever-present in modern classrooms. But for many of us teachers, we're still not sure how to feel about it. Teachers want to engage students and prepare them for the future.

- **Pro: technology gives teachers access to an endless supply of learning resources**

The internet is the 21st century classroom bookshelf. It's full of learning resources that teachers and students can access anytime; anywhere there's Wi-Fi. This access can power independent learning. Instead of just being spoon-fed the learning content in class, students can watch a YouTube tutorial at home to clarify a concept, or hone their mathematics fluency with a Mathematics lesson before dinner. It's the initiative teachers have preached for years, and it's never been more possible

- **Con: unreliable information is everywhere**

Not everything published on the internet is true (shocking, we know). But assessing the reliability of digital information is a vital soft skill in today's day and age. That's why instead of avoiding it, we need to teach our students how to critically assess what they read and hear as they navigate the digital sphere.

If you're still worried about students being led astray, it's worth using software that's been curriculum-aligned and pedagogically tested by real teachers. For example, 3P has a team of educators from all over the globe who ensure our products are explicitly mapped to regional curriculum standards.

- **Pro: technology can save teachers time**

Only once we've conquered stacks of marking, created resources, and wrestled with an uncooperative printer can we teachers get into the classroom and do what we do best.

Technology can save us that time – whether via automated marking, sourcing pre-made activities, or just cutting back on paperwork.

We can invest this extra time back into those things we never get around to; signing up for that professional learning course, having a long overdue conversation with a parent, or preparing a special support activity for the student who's been struggling all week.

Con: less Face Time

No amount of technology in the classroom can replace talented, inspired teachers. As the adage goes, any teacher that can be replaced with a tech device probably deserves to be

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replaced. Technology is not the solution to ensuring a healthy vigorous learning culture; it is simply a pedagogical tool that is only as valuable as the instructor who wields it. In fact, while billions of dollars are spent on Edtech, countries that don't deploy tech often have better educational outcomes than countries that spend heavily

Face to face interactions between teacher and student can help students not just acquire facts, but to understand, interpret, and apply these facts into useful and interesting knowledge. Through face to face interactions, teachers can help students build self-esteem and confidence and emotional maturity. Particularly in disadvantaged areas, teachers can provide a zone of comfort and security, and everywhere teachers can reduce the cyber bullying that so often accompanies social media.

Pro: saves time

Time is one of the most precious commodities for educators. By eliminating the need to commute to school during evenings and weekends, educators can spend more time on learning concepts. Digital technology saves teachers and students time.

Cons: requires Management and Training

New tech in the classroom also means needing IT professionals to help set it up, maintain it, and support teachers and students in its use. Clear and transparent communications among administration, faculty, and tech vendors that clarify how adopting a particular device, platform, or program will benefit students and teacher alike, can greatly enhance the use of technology in the classroom, to remove the suspicion that such technology is just "bells and whistles" with little actual value. Teachers also need access to training.

Moreover, institutions can help maximize their technical support staff by finding a less Resource-Intensive Solution.

Suggestions: -

We believe in a balanced approach to education: fun, but informative; technological, but hands-on; modern, yet traditional. Striking the perfect balance, our dedicated and professional educators help nurture your child's cognitive, social and emotional development, all in a safe and nurturing. More importantly, digital applications can be used by teachers to create their own learning resources. The effective use of digital learning tools in classrooms can increase student engagement, help teachers improve their lesson plans, and facilitate personalized

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learning. It also helps students build essential 21st-century skills.

Conclusion: -

Digital Technology is a versatile and valuable tool for teaching and learning and becoming a way of life. The most important thing is that teachers need to be prepared. But technology in education has its own pros and cons. Digital Technology has a very positive impact on education and at the same time may also pose negative effects. Teachers, and students should take advantage of this in the good light and eliminate the drawbacks which are pulling back many of students as well as schools from achieving excellence. It is thus time for every country to introduce a more technologically equipped education sector in the future. Growth in Digital technology is the need in today's education it's not only important for teacher but also helpful to students.

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